

Transference Number of Hydrochloric Acid in Dioxane-Water Mixtures from Electromotive Force Measurements

BIJOY KETAN DAS, UMESH CHANDRA MISHRA and P. K. DAS*

Chemistry Department, Ravenshaw College, Cuttack-753003

Manuscript received 10 February 1977, revised 22 July 1977, accepted 21 November 1977

Transference number of hydrochloric acid was determined from the study of the cell :

$$\text{Ag-AgCl} \mid \text{HCl} (m_1) \begin{matrix} \text{dioxane X\%} \\ \text{water Y\%} \end{matrix} \parallel \text{HCl} (m_2) \begin{matrix} \text{dioxane X\%} \\ \text{water Y\%} \end{matrix} \mid \text{AgCl-Ag}$$
 temperature range 25-45°, where the weight per cent of dioxane was 10, 30, 40 and 60 .
 The data at 25° compares well with those determined by Hittorf's method in the same solvent mixture.

In aqueous solution, most of the ions are hydrated and it is expected that water will be transported to the electrodes during electrolysis. Washburn number¹ gives an idea about the number of moles of water transported by the electrolyte from the anode to cathode on the passage of one faraday of electricity. It also provides valuable information on the preferential (or non-preferential) presence of water or the non-electrolytic solvent (in case of mixed solvents) in the solvation shells of the ions^{2,3}. The determination of Washburn number using Feakin's method⁴ for mixed solvent systems involving dioxane-water mixtures of various compositions requires a knowledge of cation transference number (t_+) of HCl in these solvent mixtures. So in the present investigation, the cationic transference number of hydrochloric acid in these solvent mixtures containing 10, 30, 40 and 60 weight per cent of dioxane has been determined at 25, 30, 35, 40 and 45° from the e.m.f. measurement of the cell ;

$$\text{Ag-AgCl} \mid \text{HCl} (m_1) \begin{matrix} \text{dioxane X\%} \\ \text{water Y\%} \end{matrix} \parallel \text{HCl} (m_2) \begin{matrix} \text{dioxane X\%} \\ \text{water Y\%} \end{matrix} \mid \text{AgCl-Ag}$$

(Cell-I)

The accuracy of the results were checked up in measuring the transference number by Hittorf's method at 25° three suitable concentrations of the electrolyte corresponding to each concentration of the solvent.

Experimental

Dioxane used was BDH AnalaR quality and was purified as described elsewhere⁴. Hydrochloric acid used was a Kahlbaum sample, which was diluted, distilled, the middle fraction of a constant boiling mixture was collected and was used as a stock solution to prepare solutions of desired concentration. The chloride content of the stock solution was analysed gravimetrically. All solutions were prepared in the molal scale. Ag-AgCl electrode used

was of thermal electrolytic type. An air thermostat was used in which the temperature was regulated within $\pm 0.05^\circ$. A Leeds-Northrup K-2 type potentiometer was used in conjunction with a matching galvanometer and calibrated standard cell.

The solutions in the above cell were separated by means of a stop cock of equal bore as the connecting tubes of the half cells. The cell assembly was kept inside an air thermostat maintained at the desired temperature. The connecting stop cock was opened carefully so as to establish contact between the two half cells and the e.m.f. readings were taken. Duplicate experiments were performed simultaneously in each case and the duplicates generally agreed within ± 0.1 mV. The reported e.m.f. values are the mean of the duplicates.

In determining the transference number independently by Hittorf's method, an apparatus similar to that used by Washburn⁵ was used. The other experimental procedures were followed in the usual manner.

Results and Discussion

When the concentrations of the solutions in the two half cells are 'm' and (m+dm), the e.m.f. of the cell I is given by

$$dE_t = 2t_+ \frac{RT}{F} d \ln a \quad \dots (1)$$

$$\text{or, } \frac{dE_t}{d \log a} = 2 \times 2.3026 \frac{RT}{F} t_+ \quad \dots (2)$$

where 'a' is the mean activity of the electrolyte at concentration 'm', t_+ is the transference number of HCl. The values of E_t , the e.m.f. of the cell-I when the concentration 'm₁' was fixed at 0.03M and 'm₂' was varied between 0.003M to 0.1 M, are reported in Table 1.

TABLE 1
E.M.F. OF THE CELL-I IN ABSOLUTE VOLTS
Solvent: 10% dioxane + 90% water

m	25°C	30°C	35°C	40°C	45°C
0.003	-0.09250	-0.09385	-0.09480	-0.09570	-0.09650
0.004	-0.08090	-0.08205	—	—	—
0.005	-0.07185	-0.07285	-0.07350	—	-0.07480
0.006	-0.06460	-0.06585	-0.06590	-0.06645	-0.06705
0.007	-0.05835	-0.05900	-0.05900	-0.05995	-0.06045
0.008	-0.05300	-0.05360	—	—	—
0.009	-0.04820	-0.04880	-0.04925	-0.04970	-0.05010
0.010	-0.04395	-0.04450	-0.04470	-0.04510	-0.04550
0.020	-0.01620	-0.01640	-0.01710	-0.01730	-0.01740
0.040	0.01150	0.01155	0.01250	0.01270	—
0.050	0.02035	0.02055	0.02105	0.02130	0.02145
0.060	0.02765	0.02790	0.02860	0.02900	0.02915
0.070	0.03375	0.03405	0.03470	0.03520	0.03545
0.080	0.03825	0.03945	0.04005	0.04060	0.04085
0.090	0.04375	0.04405	0.04500	0.04565	0.0 —
0.100	0.04710	0.04840	0.04940	0.05025	0.05085

30% dioxane + 70% water

0.003	-0.09030	-0.09125	-0.09195	-0.09270	-0.09350
0.004	—	-0.07970	-0.08025	-0.03090	-0.08155
0.005	-0.07000	-0.07230	-0.07120	-0.07180	-0.07200
0.006	-0.06280	-0.06340	-0.06380	-0.06430	—
0.007	-0.05670	-0.05725	-0.05755	-0.05805	-0.05850
0.008	-0.05140	-0.05195	-0.05225	-0.05265	-0.05305
0.009	-0.04685	-0.04730	—	-0.04790	—
0.010	-0.04270	-0.04310	-0.04330	-0.04370	-0.04405
0.020	-0.01570	-0.01585	-0.01600	-0.01610	-0.01625
0.040	0.01110	0.01115	—	0.01175	0.01190
0.050	0.01970	0.01985	0.02000	0.02010	0.02030
0.060	0.02660	0.02690	0.02705	0.02730	0.02745
0.070	0.03430	0.03290	0.03305	0.03335	0.03350
0.080	0.03775	0.03800	0.03830	0.03860	0.03890
0.090	0.04230	0.04260	0.04280	0.04320	0.04345
0.100	0.04640	—	0.04690	0.04730	—

40% dioxane + 60% water

0.003	-0.08705	-0.08800	-0.08870	-0.08940	-0.08985
0.004	-0.07595	-0.07670	-0.07800	-0.07790	-0.07835
0.005	-0.06735	-0.06800	-0.06795	-0.07000	-0.06970
0.006	-0.06035	-0.06100	-0.06105	—	-0.06230
0.007	-0.05450	-0.05510	-0.05520	-0.05590	-0.05615
0.008	-0.04950	-0.04995	-0.05010	-0.05060	-0.05090
0.009	-0.04495	-0.04545	-0.04560	—	-0.04630
0.010	-0.04095	-0.04150	-0.04155	-0.04195	-0.04220
0.020	-0.01500	-0.01525	-0.01580	-0.01540	-0.01545
0.040	0.01065	0.01070	0.01095	0.01085	0.01095
0.050	0.01885	0.01955	0.01910	0.01930	0.01940
0.060	0.02560	0.02580	0.02630	0.02615	0.02625
0.070	0.03120	0.03145	0.03180	0.03200	0.03210
0.080	—	0.03640	0.03685	0.03695	0.03710
0.090	—	0.04080	0.04025	0.04135	0.04155

60% dioxane + 40% water

0.003	-0.07625	-0.07670	—	—	—
0.004	-0.06625	-0.06680	-0.06640	-0.06720	-0.06680
0.005	-0.05870	-0.05915	-0.05875	-0.05950	-0.05920
0.006	-0.05165	-0.05300	-0.05250	-0.05320	-0.05295
0.007	-0.04730	-0.04770	-0.04740	-0.04795	-0.04775
0.008	-0.04290	-0.04330	-0.04295	-0.04350	-0.04330
0.009	-0.03900	-0.03935	-0.03905	-0.03960	—
0.010	—	-0.03580	-0.03560	-0.03610	-0.03585
0.020	-0.01315	-0.01330	-0.01335	-0.01350	-0.01345
0.040	0.00910	0.00945	0.00940	-0.00935	—
0.050	0.01670	0.01690	0.01690	0.01685	0.01670
0.060	0.02250	0.02275	0.02280	0.02290	0.02265
0.070	0.02770	0.02790	0.02775	0.02800	0.02800
0.080	0.03200	0.03235	0.03220	0.03280	0.03240
0.090	0.03570	0.03630	0.03635	0.03680	0.03755
0.100	0.03930	0.03995	—	0.04035	0.04095

MacInnes and Beattie⁶ have suggested that the values of E_t could be expressed as a function of the logarithm of the activities of the electrolyte. To calculate the activity at different concentrations a knowledge of activity coefficient at these concentrations are necessary. The activity coefficient values for the different concentrations used here are reported elsewhere from this laboratory⁷.

The present set of data for E_t were found to fit in an equation of the type :

$$E_t = K_1 + K_2 \log a + K_3 (\log a)^3 \quad \dots (3)$$

where K_1 , K_2 and K_3 are empirical constants and 'a' is the mean activity of HCl at molality m_2 . The equation (3) on differentiation with respect to $\log a$, becomes

$$\frac{dE_t}{d \log a} = K_2 + 3K_3 (\log a)^2 \quad \dots (4)$$

So from equations (2) and (4)

$$t_+ = \frac{K_2 + 3 K_3 (\log a)^2}{2k + \frac{3}{2} \frac{K_3}{k}} \quad \dots (5)$$

where 'k' equals $2.3026RT/F$.

The transference number so determined are recorded in Table 2. The constants of the equation (3) were calculated by the least square method and are recorded at the bottom of the Table 2.

TABLE-2
TRANSFERENCE NUMBER OF HCl IN DIOXANE-WATER MIXTURE
1% dioxane + 90% water

m	25°C	30°C	35°C	40°C	45°C
0	0.8195	0.8150	0.8125	0.8045	0.7995
0.003	0.8251	0.8205	0.8180	0.8115	0.8071
0.004	0.8262	0.8216	—	—	—
0.005	0.8270	0.8224	0.8200	—	0.8099
0.006	0.8276	0.8231	0.8207	0.8155	0.8108
0.007	0.8281	0.8236	0.8212	0.8164	0.8115
0.008	0.8285	0.8240	—	—	—
0.009	0.8289	0.8244	0.8221	0.8176	0.8126
0.010	0.8292	0.8248	0.8224	0.8181	0.8132
0.020	0.8311	0.8267	0.8245	0.8212	0.8159
0.040	0.8328	0.8283	0.8263	0.8240	—
0.050	0.8333	0.8288	0.8267	0.8247	0.8191
0.060	0.8336	0.8292	0.8272	0.8258	0.8196
0.070	0.8339	0.8295	0.8274	0.8257	0.8200
0.080	0.8341	0.8297	0.8276	0.8261	0.8203
0.090	0.8344	0.8299	0.8279	0.8264	—
0.100	0.8344	0.8301	0.8281	0.8267	0.8209
$K_1 \times 10^3$	158.35	160.51	163.09	165.72	167.39
$K_2 \times 10^3$	99.00	100.14	101.51	103.19	104.06
$K_3 \times 10^6$	-7.0	-7.3	-7.8	-12.0	-11.0

Contd.

Contd.

30% dioxane + 70% water					
m	25°C	30°C	35°C	40°C	45°C
0	0.8185	0.8129	0.8073	0.8025	0.7992
0.003	0.8250	0.8202	0.8143	0.8080	0.8040
0.004	—	0.8215	0.8155	0.8094	0.8054
0.005	0.8276	0.8223	0.8165	0.8105	0.8065
0.006	0.8284	0.8233	0.8172	0.8114	—
0.007	0.8291	0.8239	0.8178	0.8120	0.8080
0.008	0.8298	0.8245	0.8183	0.8126	0.8085
0.009	0.8303	0.8249	—	0.8131	—
0.010	0.8307	0.8253	0.8191	0.8135	0.8094
0.020	0.8342	0.8277	0.8213	0.8161	0.8119
0.040	0.8357	0.8297	—	0.8183	0.8141
0.050	0.8364	0.8303	0.8237	0.8189	0.8147
0.060	0.8369	0.8308	0.8241	0.8194	0.8152
0.070	0.8374	0.8312	0.8244	0.8197	0.8156
0.080	0.8376	0.8314	0.8249	0.8201	0.8159
0.090	0.8379	0.8317	0.8250	0.8204	0.8161
0.100	0.8382	—	0.8252	0.8206	0.8 —
$K_1 \times 10^3$	163.69	165.27	166.78	168.87	170.97
$K_2 \times 10^3$	99.59	100.46	101.22	102.40	103.50
$K_3 \times 10^5$	-10.0	-9.0	-8.5	-10.0	-10.0
40% dioxane + 60% water					
0	0.8064	0.8018	0.7986	0.7928	0.7879
0.003	0.8140	0.8100	0.8052	0.7996	0.7940
0.004	0.8153	0.8114	0.8064	0.8009	0.7953
0.005	0.8163	0.8124	0.8075	0.8018	0.7962
0.006	0.8169	0.8131	0.8082	—	0.7969
0.007	0.8175	0.8143	0.8093	0.8032	0.7975
0.008	0.8180	0.8147	0.8094	0.8037	0.7980
0.009	0.8185	0.8151	0.8098	—	0.7985
0.010	0.8189	0.8175	0.8102	0.8045	0.7988
0.020	0.8212	0.8187	0.8125	0.8068	0.8011
0.040	0.8231	0.8195	0.8145	0.8087	0.8030
0.050	0.8236	0.8201	0.8150	0.8093	0.8035
0.060	0.8241	0.8205	0.8155	0.8098	0.8039
0.070	0.8245	0.8209	0.8159	0.8108	0.8043
0.080	—	0.8212	0.8161	0.8104	0.8046
0.090	—	0.8214	0.8163	0.8106	0.8048
$K_1 \times 10^3$	164.70	167.02	169.19	170.84	172.77
$K_2 \times 10^3$	98.02	99.26	100.23	101.18	102.06
$K_3 \times 10^5$	-8.5	-9.0	-9.0	-9.0	-9.0
60% dioxane + 40% water					
0	0.7717	0.7677	0.7618	0.7587	0.7528
0.003	0.7850	0.7800	—	—	—
0.004	0.7870	0.7822	0.7775	0.7735	0.7687
0.005	0.7886	0.7839	0.7793	0.7752	0.7706
0.006	0.7899	0.7851	0.7807	0.7766	0.7721
0.007	0.7908	0.7862	0.7818	0.7777	0.7734
0.008	0.7917	0.7871	0.7827	0.7787	0.7744
0.009	0.7924	0.7878	0.7837	0.7795	—
0.010	—	0.7885	0.7844	0.7802	0.7760
0.020	0.7969	0.7947	0.7888	0.7846	0.7806
0.040	0.8002	0.7961	0.7927	0.7884	—
0.050	0.8012	0.7971	0.7938	0.7896	0.7861
0.060	0.8010	0.7979	0.7947	0.7904	0.7871
0.070	0.8025	0.7985	0.7955	0.7912	0.7878
0.080	0.8030	0.7992	0.7961	0.7918	0.7890
0.090	0.8034	0.7997	0.7966	0.7924	0.7893
0.100	0.8038	0.8001	—	0.7928	0.7897
$K_1 \times 10^3$	176.13	178.54	182.65	185.13	189.40
$K_2 \times 10^3$	96.06	97.23	98.57	99.67	101.02
$K_3 \times 10^5$	-15.0	-16.0	-18.0	-18.0	-20.0

The results of the transference number measured by Hittorf's method at concentrations 0.05, 0.08 and 0.10M at 25° are recorded in Table 3 together with the values found by e.m.f. method for comparison. The results were found to be in good agreement with each other.

TABLE 3—TRANSFERENCE NUMBER OF HCl AT 25°, DETERMINED BY E. M. F. AND HITTORF'S METHOD

Wt. % dioxane	10%	30%	40%	60%
E. M. F. Method				
m				
0.05	0.8333	0.8364	0.8236	0.8010
0.08	0.8341	0.8376	—	0.8030
0.10	0.8344	0.8382	—	0.8040
Hittorf's Method				
m				
0.05	0.8340	0.8362	0.8240	0.8013
0.08	0.8342	0.8372	—	0.8034
0.10	0.8348	0.8387	—	0.8047

It is known that the transference number vary with the concentration of the electrolyte and the following relationship^a was verified to represent the variation :

$$t_+ = t_+^0 - Ac^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (6)$$

where t_+ and t_+^0 are the transference numbers of a given ion in a solution of concentration 'm' and at infinite dilution respectively ; 'A' is a constant and 'c' is the molar concentration corresponding to molality 'm' and was calculated from the density of the solution. A similar expression which holds good up to relatively high concentrations, is given by Jones and Dole^a is :

$$\frac{t_+^0 + 1}{t_+ + 1} = 1 + Bc^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad \dots (7)$$

The two equations (equations 6 & 7) were used to determine the values of t_+^0 by suitable plots and the two t_+^0 values obtained by extrapolation were found to be in good agreement and the values for t_+^0 are reported in Table 2.

References

1. J. N. AGAR, "The Structure of Electrolytic Solutions", Wiley, N. Y. 1959, p. 218.
2. K. H. KHOO, *J. Chem. Soc., Far. I*, 1975, 446.
3. D. FRANKS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 5308.
4. S. C. MOHANTY, U. C. MISHRA, K. C. SINGH and P. K. DAS, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, 50, 302.
5. E. W. WASHBURN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 31, 322.
6. D. A. MACINNES and J. A. BEATTIE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 42, 1117.
7. U. C. MISHRA and P. K. DAS, *Electrochim. Acta.*, 1977, 22, 59.
8. S. GLASSTONE, "An Introduction to Electrochemistry", Affiliated East-West Press, New-Delhi, 1968, p. 123.
9. JONES and DOLE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 51, 1073.